

Insomnia and Related Anxiety among Medical Students

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Abstract

Objective: Objective of this study is to determine the prevalence of insomnia in medical students and also to identify anxiety related insomnia.

Method: This is a cross sectional study to determine prevalence of insomnia in medical students with sample size of 190 students. Questionnaire consisted of socio-demographic characteristics along with questions related to insomnia for anxiety.

Result: Students with sub-threshold, moderate and severe insomnia were 48.9%, 17.4%, 3.7% respectively. 50% students who were insomniacs had mild anxiety.

Conclusion: Study concludes that prevalence of insomnia in medical students are high. There is significant association between insomnia and anxiety.

Keywords: Insomnia, anxiety

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Introduction

Insomnia is defined as persistent problems in falling asleep, maintaining, or poor quality of sleep. It occurs as a result of multiple environmental, medical, psychological and mental disorders [1]. Insomnia in youth and adolescence is poorly recognized, under diagnosed and under-treated. Sleep serves various brain functions, including neurons communication with each other. Studies have stated that sleep plays a very important role in removing toxins from the brain that build up while the person is awake [2]. Sleep deprivation may cause disruption in the brain EEG recordings by affecting the biological rhythm [3]. Gumustekin reported that sleep deprivation

may delay wound healing [4]. Many studies demonstrated the effect of short duration of sleep and increased risk of hypertension and acute myocardial infarction [5,6]. Sleep deprivation can disrupt the autonomic control of heart rhythm and predispose to various cardiovascular diseases [7]. It may also cause sympatho-vagal imbalances by affecting the biological rhythm due to work shift [8]. Insomnia is considered as a nocturnal disorder that have an impact on individual's performance during waking time, taking the physical and cognitive functions that sleep usually provides [9,10]. Insomnia related disorders are associated with depressive illnesses, psychiatric problems and is an independent

risk factor for suicide and substance abuse [11-15]. Prevalence of insomnia differs with different age and gender. In Elderly patients, female gender and excessive tea consumption is associated with increased risk of insomnia [16,17]. Various studies have shown that insomnia is more prevalent in females than in males and majority is from the young age group [18]. According to various other studies, 59% of young adults from 18 to 29 years of age cannot fall asleep early at night, and not getting enough sleep [19,20]. A study conducted on medical students of medical colleges was done to assess sleep habits during clinical years, which showed that students acquired an average of 5.8 hours of sleep each night, with an average bedtime at 01:50 am. Medical students tend to reduce their sleep, in an effort to adjust with the workload and stressful environment while some reduce the sleeping time in order to have an extra hours for studying especially before exams [21,22]. Insomnia is an emerging problem that interferes with students' performance and predispose to various psychological problems. The objective of this study is to determine the prevalence of insomnia

among Medical students of Pacific Institute of Medical Sciences, Udaipur to identify the rate of anxiety-related insomnia.

Materials and Methods

This is a cross sectional study to determine the prevalence of Insomnia in medical students of Pacific Institute of Medical Sciences, Udaipur. Students of both sexes were included in this study. Sample size is 190, taken by simple random sampling using the table of random selection. Data were collected by a pre-tested questionnaire after obtaining ethics approval from the ethical committee of the institute. The questionnaires consisted of socio-demographic characteristics along with questions related to insomnia and anxiety. Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS) was included in the questionnaire [23]. The State Anxiety Scale (S-Anxiety) was employed for anxiety [24]. Descriptive statistics was used. For qualitative data, comparisons between groups were determined using the chi-square test and p value less than 0.05 was considered as significant.

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the students

Characteristics	Number	Percentage
Gender		
Male	145	76.3
Female	45	23.7
Total	190	100.0
Academic year		
First year	44	23.2
Second year	33	17.4
Third year	35	18.4
Final year	42	22.1
Intern	36	18.9
Total	190	100.0

Table 2: Insomnia among medical students

Category	Number	Percentage
No clinically significant insomnia	57	30.0
Subthreshold insomnia	93	48.9
Moderate clinical insomnia	33	17.4
Severe clinical insomnia	7	3.7

Results

The sample size was 190 out of which 145 (76.3%) were male and 45 (23.7%) were female students. About 23.2% students were from 1st year, 17.4% were from 2nd year, 18.4% were from 3rd year, 22.1% were from final year, and 18.9% were Interns. Students with no clinically significant insomnia were 57 (30%). Students with moderate clinical and severe insomnia were 17.4% and 3.7% respectively. 31.6% of the students have no difficulty in falling asleep while 25.8%

have mild difficulty. Students with severe and very severe difficulty in falling asleep were 14 (7.4%) and 12 (6.3%) respectively. In waking early, 27.4% of students have no problems in waking early while those who have severe and very severe problem in waking up early were 14.2% and 11.1% respectively. About 50% of students who were insomniacs had mild anxiety. 72.1% and 91.5% who had moderate and severe anxiety had insomnia respectively.

Table 3: Insomnia and anxiety comorbidity

Anxiety	Insomnia		Total	Chi square	P value
	Yes	No			
	NO.	NO.			
Mild	35	35	70	42.054	<0.001
Moderate	44	17	61		
Severe	54	5	59		

Discussion

This study was done to study the prevalence of insomnia among medical college students. Our result shows that more than 2/3rd of the students (70%) are insomniacs. In a study by Sing the rate of insomnia was 68.6% among Hong Kong college students [14]. In another study, Almojali reported that 76% of students in a medical college were insomniac [21]. The reasons behind medical students sleep deprivation is due to pre-sleep cognitions such as active thinking, worrying, and analyzing problems [25]. Lichstein suggested that intrusive cognitions are far more prevalent than somatic factors in creating insomnia [26]. Our study show that students who are insomniac and having severe anxiety were 54 (91.5%), and prevalence of insomnia increases as the anxiety increases from mild to moderate to severe ($p < 0.001$). Alblhal concluded that insufficient sleep and daytime sleepiness can lead to problems like interpersonal relationship, anxiety and depression [27]. Another study done

earlier by Ford reported that 40% of those with insomnia and 46.5% of those with hypersomnia had anxiety and others psychiatric disorders compared with those with no sleep complaints [2829].

Conclusion

Our study concludes that the prevalence of insomnia among medical students is high. There is also a significant association between insomnia and anxiety. More than half of students complain of insomnia and anxiety comorbidity. Management of insomnia consists of improving sleep habits, counseling, behavior therapy and identifying underlying causes.

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